

UV IMAGING FOR INTRAOPERATIVE TUMOR DELINEATION

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ABSTRACT

Locating the borders of intra-axial brain tumors, intraoperatively, has continuously been a challenge for neurosurgeons. Intraoperative MRIs, CTs, and ultrasounds are widely acceptable tools that demonstrate both advantages and disadvantages. Utilizing Ultraviolet (UV) illumination detection, via UV cameras, permits for intraoperative identification of tumors along the brain surface. Under UV illumination, the camera is capable of recording images that are processed, in order, to detect the location and extent of a cancerous tumor. This technology can locate these tumors through detecting variations of the auto-fluorescent reduced form of Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide (NADH) between normal and cancerous cells. It is reported that the NADH absorption range is at 320 nm-380 nm, and that NADH emits fluorescent light at 420 nm-480 nm. The image data is then processed in a general purpose programmable computer. Using this technology not only helps neurosurgeons to discover and delineate the borders of brain tumors intraoperatively, but also decreases surgery time as well as surgical complications.

BACKGROUND

Facilitating tumor resection and related procedures via computed tomography scans (CT), magnetic resonance image scans (MRI), positron emission tomography scans (PET), and ultrasounds generally provide pre- and post-operative information regarding the degree of invasiveness, as well as, the location of a tumor. However, 31% of anaplastic astrocytomas (intermediate-grade), 4% of glioblastoma multiforme (high grade), and most of the low grade astrocytoma do not appear vividly on CTs or MRIs even after a contrast reagent is injected into the patient. PET scans cannot be utilized intraoperatively; in addition, ultrasounds are limited by signal artifacts caused by blood and surgical trauma at the resection margin once the resection commences. Fluorescence dyes, time resolved laser induced fluorescence spectroscopy and laser-induced fluorescence of the photosensitizer, hematoporphyrin derivative, have also been used to delineate various tumors of the lung, bladder, colon, as well as the brain from normal tissue. Unfortunately, since photosensitizers require a specific light sensitive compound, there needs to be improved systems and methods in order to develop useful, enhanced images of cancerous regions in vivo. UV imaging detection for brain tumors was inspired by the two-photon auto-fluorescence dynamics imaging that demonstrated sensitivity of intracellular concentrations of NADH, along with conformations to cell physiology at the single-cell level.

METHODS

This development intends to utilize a UV/Visible camera, which has been tested at room temperature, in the operating room, in order to differentiate between tumorous and healthy tissue. This intraoperative procedure evaluates the presence of brain tumors via high resolution UV cameras, (1 k x 1 k pixels), that identify fluctuations in reflection/ fluorescence differences between tumorous and normal brain tissue. A UV-Nikkor 105mm f/4.5 lens, composed of fluorite and quartz glass, was utilized and positioned near the surgical field, in order to record the images during any tumor exposure and resection.

IRB was executed at Cedars-Sinai Medical Center .

Manual focusing of the lens requires turning on room lights and focusing the lens accordingly, while also checking the live image via Video Savant. We have used this UV imaging in two cases at Cedars-Sinai Medical Center to evaluate the appropriate distance required between the camera and the surgical field, as well as the intensity of the fluorescent light source that should be provided in the operating room.

Figure 1
Healthy brain tissue and malignant tumor tissue autofluorescence emission following excitation at 337.1 nm, showing a 15 nm peak shift between the two.

Figure 2
Demarcation of brain tissue by Neurosurgeons/researchers (Drs. Black, Chu, and Kateb) from Cedars-Sinai Medical Center and the Maxine Dunitz Neurosurgical Institute utilizing an adapted UV camera from NASA's JPL, California Institute of Technology. Based on the delta doping technology, JPL's UV imaging technology provides high sensitivity and stability across the entire UV spectral range.

RESULTS

From our results, it is recommended to reduce the distance between the surgical site and the camera, while providing an external UV emission source, in order to improve the resulting images. It is more beneficial to integrate the camera with a microscope to better enhance the surgical field image via visible light, which also provides the surgeon with improved visibility during the procedure, as well as, enable the camera to accurately provide images that clearly distinguish healthy from cancerous tissue through the microscope. The current technology integrated with multimodality imaging by Smart Microscopy inc .

DISCUSSION

Complete tumor resection is one of the most significant variables that affect the quality of life and survival of patients with gliomas. Recent advances in neuroimaging have opened new opportunities for neurosurgeons to obtain more extensive information regarding the location, invasiveness, and metabolic properties of brain tumors. Unfortunately, current techniques still cannot provide real-time intraoperative feedback about regarding the complete success of the resection. According to principles of the invention, intraoperative use of a UV camera is expected to enable neurosurgeons to attain a near total tumor resection to improve clinical outcome. Previous experimental studies have resulted in the development of similar techniques involving UV observations with other instruments that allow for optical imaging of human skin cancer. In cancerous tissue, there is an upregulation of NADH triggered by fluctuations in metabolic activities in cancerous cells as compared to normal cells (i.e., skin cancer), which can easily be detected via an ultraviolet/optical camera. This special type of UV/Optical camera plays a significant role in assisting neurosurgeons to outline the tumor margins by generating a metabolic map of the tumor that is vividly differentiable from the normal surrounding brain tissue.

CONCLUSIONS

Ultraviolet imaging (UVI) of brain tissue is anticipated to be a useful instrument for intraoperative delineation of tumor resection margins. Varying fluctuations of an auto-fluorescent reduced form of NADH can be detected between normal and cancerous cells. It is expected that this technology will be able to decrease operation time and increase the possibility of gross total resection of intra-axial brain tumors.

Figure 3
Wave Spectrum

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